

TABLE 1—N-(2'-NITRO-4,5-DIMETHOXY BENZOYL) GLYCINE HYDRAZONES*

Sl. No.	R	R'	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	Nitrogen %	
					Found	Calcd.
1.	H	C ₆ H ₅	158	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₆	14.32	14.50
2.	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄	170	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₇	13.06	13.46
3.	H	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	247	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₆ Cl	13.11	13.31
4.	H	<i>o,p</i> -Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃	220	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₆ Cl ₂	12.15	12.30
5.	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	238	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₈	16.12	16.24
6*	H	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ , <i>m,p</i> -(OCH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	173	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₁₀	14.05	14.25
7.	H	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃ , <i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	137	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₈	12.54	12.96
8.	H	<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	221	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₇	13.61	13.93
9.	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	135	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₆	14.32	14.00
10*	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	177	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₆	14.15	14.00
11.	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	121	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₆	13.22	13.52
12.	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	142	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₆ Cl	12.53	12.88
13*	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	186	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₇	13.35	13.02
14.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	181	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₆	12.32	12.12

*Yields ranged between 45-60%.

*Satisfactory analysis for C and H.

Showed ir spectral bands at 1700-1650 cm⁻¹ (C=O amide); 3350-3100 cm⁻¹ (Sec. N-H); 1650-1510 cm⁻¹ (C=N-).

cytometer count were inoculated at the bottom of the tubes and the tubes were incubated at 37° in an upright position. Vigorously growing cultures of amoebae from 72 hrs old tubes were used for inoculating the media containing the test compounds. The method of testing the action of drugs on trophozoites of *E. histolytica* is as follows :

One ml of the test solution was added to 8 ml of modified TPS-1 medium containing 0.2% cystine in screw capped tubes and then mixed by inverting the tubes. The tubes were left in an upright position overnight in order to absorb the dissolved atmospheric oxygen. 1.0 ml of the inoculum, containing 10,000 amoebae was then added to the bottom of the tubes. The tubes were incubated in an upright position at 37° without inverting them. The amoebicidal end point was determined microscopically during 72 hrs under an inverted microscope. In doubtful cases subcultures were made. In each set of experiments, tubes in duplicate at each dilution of a compound and two controls were included. The standard drugs used were emetine hydrochloride and metronidazole.

Result

Of the fourteen compounds synthesised, only three compounds no. 6, 8 and 12 (Table 1) showed an amoebicidal activity at 125 µg/ml as compared to 62.5 µg/ml and 7.8 µg/ml of emetine hydrochloride and metronidazole respectively.

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Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of Some New Mannich Bases Derived from 7-Hydroxy-4-Phenyl Coumarin

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COUMARINS are known to possess antifungal and antibacterial properties^{1,2}. 7-Hydroxy-4-phenyl coumarin, a naturally occurring coumarin, was found

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to possess antibacterial activity⁸. Several Mannich bases from benzalacetones were reported to possess bacteriostatic activity⁴. Literature revealed that only one Mannich base was synthesised from 7-hydroxy-4-phenyl coumarin⁵ and the group entered into 8-position^{6,7,8}. It was therefore considered worthwhile to synthesise the Mannich bases of 7-hydroxy-4-phenylcoumarin with a view to enhance the pharmacological activity of the original coumarins.

7-Hydroxy-4-phenyl coumarin was prepared from ethyl benzoylacetate and resorcinol by Pechmann condensation⁹. The Mannich bases were prepared by refluxing the coumarin with formalin and an amine in acetic acid¹⁰ on a water-bath. The yields of the products have almost been quantitative. These compounds were characterised from their physical and

Experimental

Melting points were uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer 237 Model. The nmr spectra were recorded on Varian 60 MHz NMR in CDCl_3 using TMS as internal standard.

Mannich bases of 7-hydroxy-4-phenylcoumarin (II, Table 1) : *General procedure* : A Mixture of 7-hydroxy-4-phenylcoumarin (0.5 g), amine (0.5 g), acetic acid (2 ml) and formaldehyde (0.5 ml) was heated on a water-bath for 7 hrs. After cooling, water (20 ml) was added and the solution was neutralized with saturated aqueous K_2CO_3 . The base was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from alcohol.

Biological screening results : All the compounds reported in Table 1 were tested *in vitro* for their antibacterial activity by tube dilution method and antifungal activity by agar dilution assay method¹². The bacteria employed were *Streptococcus faecalis* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and the fungi used were *Candida albicans*, *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* and *Aspergillus fumigatus*.

All the Mannich bases of 7-hydroxy-4-phenylcoumarin showed no activity against any of these microorganisms at 100 ppm. However, they showed activity at a higher concentration of 500 ppm. Among the

TABLE I—7-HYDROXY-8-SUBSTITUTED AMINOMETHYL-4-PHENYL COUMARIN

Compound No.	NRR'	m p. °C	Mol. Wt.	Nitrogen %		Spectra		
				Calculated	Found	Stretching frequency of (in cm^{-1})	O-H	Lactonyl C=O
II a	N-Ethyl anilino	260 ⁺	390.59	3.59	3.52	3395-3380	1725	1120
II b	<i>o</i> -Cyano anilino	95	367.38	7.63	7.56	3425-3400	1725	1330
II c	Benzyl amino	142	350.40	3.99	3.98	3450-3400	1720	1270
II d	<i>o</i> -Ethoxy anilino	146	386.43	3.62	3.59	3400-3340	1720	1080
II e	Methyl amino	270	280.3	4.99	5.01	3420-3400	1715	1280
II f	Di- <i>n</i> -butyl amino	110	378.49	3.70	3.65	3430-3415	1720	1080
II g	Diethanolamino	320 ⁺	354.38	3.95	3.86	3425-3400	1725	1130
II h	Morpholino	54	350.37	7.99	8.03	3450-3420	1730	1140
II i	Dimethylamino*	252	330.79	4.23	4.15	3120-3100	1700	1005
II j	Diethylamino*	242	358.84	3.90	3.76	3150-3120	1710	1003

* Hydrochlorides

⁺ Decomposed

analytical data. All the compounds gave consistent N analysis (Table 1). Their structures were further confirmed by ir spectra which showed the characteristic absorption bands around 3400-3360 cm^{-1} (hydrogen bonded OH stretching frequency) and 1700 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl) and 1330-1003 cm^{-1} (C-N stretching). Further the nmr spectra shows the absence of a signal at δ 6.7-6.8 corresponding to C_8 proton of coumarin¹¹ confirming their structures as 8-alkylaminomethyl-7-hydroxy-4-phenyl coumarins.

All the compounds reported in Table I were screened *in vitro* for their antibacterial and antifungal activities.

compounds 8-morpholinomethyl-7-hydroxy-4-phenyl coumarin and 8-benzylaminomethyl-7-hydroxy-4-phenyl coumarins were more active against *S. faecalis* and *K. pneumoniae*. They also exhibited moderate antifungal activity against *T. mentagrophytes* and *Aspergillus fumigatus* but were inactive against *C. albicans*.

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R = H, acyl or alkyl
R' = H or alkyl
X = O or H₂

Antifungal activity: *In vitro* antifungal activity was determined by a two fold serial dilution method⁴ against *T. mentagrophytes*, *M. canis*, *C. neoformans* and *H. capsulatum*; amphotericin B being selected for serving as the sensitivity control.

The minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) expressed as mcg/ml of the different pyridazines (II) are shown in Table 1.

Experimental

2,3,4,4a-Tetrahydro-3-oxo-5H-indeno[1,2-c]pyridazine (I): A mixture of ethyl 1-oxo-indan-2-ylacetate (14 g, 0.075 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (80%, 6.3 ml) was refluxed in alcohol for 6 hrs. Alcohol was distilled off and the residual yellow material crystallised (charcoal) from boiling water to give (I) in colourless plates (9.0 g, 76%), m.p. 188°; ν (Nujol) 3250 (NH), 1680 cm^{-1} (amide CO); PMR (CDCl_3): τ 6.5-8 (m, 5H, $\text{CH}_2\text{-CH-CH}_2$); 2.1-2.7 (m, 4H, ArH); 0.75 (s, 1H NH). In presence of D_2O the peak at τ 0.75 disappeared.

1,2,3,4,4a,9b-Hexahydro-3-oxo-5H-indeno [1,2-c]pyridazine (II, R=R'=H, X=O): The above pyridazine (I) (11.2 g, 0.06 mol) dissolved in absolute alcohol (100 ml) was hydrogenated at 45 lbs pressure of hydrogen with the addition of 3 drops of concentrated HCl and palladium charcoal (0.5 g, 10%). After consumption of theoretical amount of hydrogen, the catalyst was filtered out, alcohol distilled off completely, and the product (II, R=R'=H, X=O) crystallised from benzene-light petroleum in fine needle shaped crystals (10.5 g, 91%), m.p. 169-170°; ν (Nujol) 3250, 3350 (NH), 1680 cm^{-1} (amide CO). [Found: C, 70.6; H, 6.1; N, 14.71. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires C, 70.2; H, 6.38; N, 14.84%].

Synthesis of Indeno [1,2-c] Pyridazines as Possible Antifungal Agents

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TAKAHASHI and co-workers^{1,2} observed high *in vitro* antimycotic activity in some arylpyridazines. Again, high *in vitro* antifungal activity of undec-10-enylindan hydrochloride was also demonstrated³. So it was considered worthwhile to synthesize some indeno-pyridazine derivatives (II) and to investigate their antifungal activity, if any.

Ethyl 1-oxo-indan-2-ylacetate was condensed with hydrazine to give the pyridazine (I). This structure was ascertained by its pmr spectrum. It was hydrogenated to [II, R=R'=H, X=O]. The latter was acylated with undec-10-enoic acid chloride to give the amide [II, R=CO(CH₂)₉CH=CH₂, R'=H, X=O], the amide functions of which were reduced with LAH and the resultant hexahydroindeno-pyridazine [II, R=(CH₂)₉CH=CH₂, R'=H, X=H₂] was further alkylated.

TABLE 1—ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY OF THE PYRIDAZINES (II)

Sl. No.	R	R'	X	Minimum <i>in vitro</i> inhibitory concn. (mcg/ml)			
				<i>T. mentagrophytes</i>	<i>M. canis</i>	<i>C. neoformans</i>	<i>H. capsulatum</i>
1.	H	H	O	n	n	n	n
2.	CO(CH ₂) ₉ CH=CH ₂	H	O	n	n	n	n
3.	(CH ₂) ₉ CH=CH ₂	H	H ₂	50	n	12.5	12.5
4.	(CH ₂) ₉ CH=CH ₂	CH ₃	H ₂	50	25	n	n
5.	(CH ₂) ₉ CH=CH ₂	C ₂ H ₅	H ₂	100	12.5	n	n
6.	(CH ₂) ₉ CH=CH ₂	n-C ₃ H ₇	H ₂	50	n	n	100
7.	Amphotericin B	—	—	6.25	0.25	1.0	0.5

n = no activity upto 100 mcg/ml.